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VARIABLES AFFECTING EXPORT SATISFACTION-AN INTEGRATED MODEL FOR THE EXPORT SUCCESS

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ABSTRACT

Exports help a nation's economy grow and provide businesses a competitive edge in the global marketplace when it comes to generating foreign money. Increasing export sales volume is crucial for a country's growth since it closes the gap in international commerce, boosts employment and output, and aids in the country's overall progress. The main objectives of the present research are to find out the impact of company's export capabilities and export strategies on satisfaction with export success. There were 100 export managers were targeted in the firms specially focusing on export orientation as a samples. Structured questionnaire was issued to each respondents to collect the data. Both primary and secondary data was collected for the study purpose. Multiple regression equation was used as analysis tool in the present study. It is found that, the unique contribution for the variables such as company's export capabilities and export strategies were significantly influencing in predicting satisfaction with export success.

Keywords: Impact, Export Capabilities, Export Strategies, Satisfaction, Export Success.

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1. INTRODUCTION

To encourage exports and allow private companies to participate in global marketplaces, every government in the world creates export policies (Workman, D. 2017). Manufacturing sectors look for one or the other way to sell their goods in international markets with the help of export policies in order to thrive in fierce competition. Finding and satisfying the unique needs of overseas clients

is a standard marketing strategy in global markets (U.S. Department of Commerce 2016). Another name for this practice is export marketing. Export marketing improves the nation's and businesses' reputations and goodwill while lowering the risk burden. Out of all the industries, the automotive sector is a significant one with close ties to the capital equipment and services sectors (Thakkar, K. and Mukherjee, S. 2018). Over the past ten years, the global vehicle sector has experienced a notable increase in exports. One of the driving forces behind its expansion is the possibility of generating foreign exchange through exports (Singh, V. 2017). According to the legal procedures developed by the importing and exporting countries, export marketing is defined as "the organized process of exporting of manufactured goods to the other countries by various modes of exports, the process which includes complex rules and regulations." Many studies on the export marketing techniques of different sectors have been conducted during the last ten years (Saber, B. 2018). The issue of variables influencing export success was covered in the majority of the study publications. In order to improve export performance and lower the failure rate of an export enterprise, some study writers have simplified a large number of export behavior determinants (Saranga, H. 2015). In both local and foreign contexts, management decision-making is supported by the effect of export marketing information (Sultana, M. and Ibrahim, A.K. 2015). The understanding of export performance has expanded beyond competitive advantage metrics as global competition intensifies innovation and knowledge base, emphasizing the impact of marketing strategies on global competitiveness, particularly in the manufacturing sector. By hosting trade fairs and exhibits and participating in auto expos, India's manufacturing sector is concentrating on innovation and design to thrive and establish itself in the international market (Saber, B. 2018). With the help of several initiatives, the industry is getting ready to advance and become a top-tier provider of manufactured products (Mishra, P.C. 2018).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Karnataka State manufacturing enterprises are leveraging IT industry help to establish export competency in the form of product simulation and testing software in order to obtain an appealing market position in the worldwide market (Dhawan, R.G. and Huddar, S.N. 2018). With the aid of chip designs, advanced CAD software is used for product design and drawings for installing embedded systems in luxury car sectors. By demonstrating and persuading technical talents in international marketplaces, the industry has added value to the automotive sector (Divakaran, P. and Muthukumar, M. 2018). Many Karnataka State manufacturing suppliers now use this as a marketing tool. In order to satisfy the demands of their international clientele, multinational corporations such as Delphi and Bosch are taking advantage of this opportunity and establishing their research facilities with the assistance of Karnataka State manufacturing suppliers (ET-Auto Report 2018). Cost leadership is a tactic used by manufacturers to draw in international clients. Karnataka State manufacturers are obtaining technology through technical partnerships with OEMs if they are unable to satisfy certain standards. To service OEMs, financially sound companies are establishing manufacturing units near them (Mishra, P.C. 2018). Karnataka state manufacturers have a lot of opportunities for items including sheet metal, brake lines, forging, casting, pistons, and piston rings. According to Saber (2018), the key to success in global markets

is a low-cost, superior-quality approach. When the value of the rupee rises relative to the dollar, Karnataka state manufacturers export to developed nations. In order to market and distribute their manufactured goods, component manufacturers are expanding into international markets using patents, trademarks, and intellectual property rights (Thakkar, K. and Mukherjee, S. 2018). Manufacturers used to export based on unsolicited orders for many years, but these days the trend has shifted, and export managers are stepping up to commit to contacting and communicating with OEMs overseas through technical presentations, advertising, trade journals, websites, and business directories (Tripathy, A. Shanker, B 2018). Manufacturers in the Karnataka State are working to expand their product line in order to provide OEMs with integrated solutions. Because of technical defenses in each area, they also modify their marketing approach according to the market features in each nation. To cut costs, several businesses are adopting a standardization strategy for their products. The producers are creating complex marketing strategies to position their goods globally. The manufacturing sector produces two types of goods: general products and particular products (Alen, L. 2017). Specific product manufacturing necessitates a high level of adaptability. It is made possible by the adaptability of technology. General product manufacturing necessitates a high level of product uniformity. Before the OEMs receive large orders, samples of design-based items are shown (Altun, I. 2017). This is how produced items are traditionally marketed overseas. When payments are certain, manufacturers prefer to export their goods. The GDP of the customer's nation serves as a factor for selecting the export destination as it shows their ability to make purchases and make payments (Chouhan, S. 2017). As a first-mover advantage, freshly developed items typically have high prices that aid in ROI recovery. Negotiations, quotations, closed bids, quality conditions, distance, credit policy, order size, length of commitment to place export order, degree of middlemen intervention, government policies of both countries, economic conditions such as business cycles and inflation, corporate policies, cost of materials, engineer feasibility analysis report, taxes and tariffs, technical complexity in manufacturing, level of competition, etc. are all factors that determine the prices for the export market in the manufacturing industry (CII Industrial Report 2017). In order to accommodate clients, the sector occasionally uses a uniform pricing structure. Prices are often set in accordance with domestic market pricing standards. Manufacturers use their own subsidiaries near OEMs as part of their global distribution strategy (Dash, A. and Chanda, R 2017). It saves money and circumvents international procedural obstacles. Third-party warehousing arrangements will be made if the OEMs place a lot of export orders in a short amount of time. They designate local representatives to distribute components. In order to find market opportunities, businesses may set up their own sales offices overseas (Dash, A. and Chanda, R. 2017). Manufacturers uncover possible export markets by identifying overseas brokers on a commission basis during the manufacturing distribution process. To save money, a lot of manufacturers favor direct exports. In this business, supplying components through technical cooperation and joint ventures is a commonly recognized distribution approach (Is'haq, A.Y., Ahassanul, A. K., and Haque, M. 2017). In terms of logistics, the vast majority of producers employ shipping. In the form of information sharing about international markets, the industry receives limited institutional backing. Export market features influence distribution

standardization and adaptation (Kahia, M. 2017). By visiting customers and describing their technological know-how, Karnataka State firms are employing promotion techniques. According to Karunakar (2017), the majority of component suppliers participate in international trade fairs and attend international exhibits. Emails, video conferencing, and other means are used to build customer networks. The industry provides promotional assistance to foreign representatives in the form of funding, training, joint advertising, and other things. To interact with overseas clients, visiting cards and technical brochures are utilized (Khaire, M.V. 2017). One of the most important advantages when speaking with international clients is managerial language competency. Information sharing about international markets provides the sector with a reasonable level of institutional assistance. Export market features influence the standardization and adaption of distribution (Kahia, M. 2017). Manufacturers in the Karnataka State are utilizing advertising tactics by visiting customers and outlining their technological know-how. The majority of component suppliers engage in international trade events and attend international exhibits (Karunakar, B. 2017). Through video conferencing, emails, and other means, customer networks are developed. Foreign representatives receive promotional help from the industry in the form of funding, training, joint advertising, and other means. Technical brochures and visiting cards are utilized to interact with international clients (Khaire, M.V. 2017). One of a manager's main advantages when speaking with international clients is their command of the language. According to Singh (2017), well-established companies with a solid resource basis, sufficient export expertise, and a modified export market strategy performed well abroad. The main factors influencing export performance, according to Tiwari, R. and Kalogerakis, K. (2017), are managerial traits like managers' export commitment, export knowledge, export motivation, and product attributes, as well as firm traits like the firm's internationalization, innovation, and export marketing capabilities (Tolmay, A.S and Venter, P 2017). believe that a company's size, assets, financial stability, and product range are all significant factors that affect its capacity to succeed internationally (Workman, D. 2017). He goes on to say that the bigger a company is, the more likely it is that it will be able to innovate, create goods with new features, and provide after-sales support by becoming a technological leader via research and development. This may also be utilized as a strategy for export orientation. According to (Erdila, S.T. and Ozdemir, O. 2016), a number of study findings demonstrated that company attributes, environmental attributes, and export commitment had a beneficial impact on export performance (IBEF Report 2016). The goal of this study is to determine how the export performance of domestic enterprises differs from their company characteristics. Key factors influencing export success include company size, technical intensity, vertical and horizontal integration, capital expenditure, import volume, and the nation's export strategy. International market data, marketing research, export market segmentation, targeting, positioning, and product attributes are all important factors in improving small businesses' export performance, according to (Kumar, G. 2016). analyzes that the following firm characteristics are regarded as important factors in achieving the export goal: firm age, the firm's level of international exposure, technical expertise, ongoing export engagement, firm size, cost of export operation, export operational efficiency, and the seriousness of export marketing (Invest

Karnataka, 2016).

3. RESEARCH PROBLEM

Following a thorough analysis of the literature, no particular export marketing tactics were discovered. There are several elements influencing Bengaluru City's manufacturing industry's export marketing. An integrated research model for export business was further aided by the lack of specialized studies on firm-related characteristics and export marketing aspects that contribute to Satisfaction with Export success. Fewer studies have been conducted on the variables influencing Bengaluru City's industrial industries' Satisfaction with Export success.

4. NEED FOR THE STUDY

Finding the drivers and elements influencing successful international company has become essential, particularly from the standpoint of export orientation. Export managers may be able to lessen the difficulties and uncertainties presented by foreign markets if they can identify the internal and external elements influencing international business. Regarding the impact of firm-related variables and export marketing components on Satisfaction with Export success, no research paper has been published. Understanding the research on how firm-related characteristics and export marketing components affect Satisfaction with Export success is essential to preventing export marketing failures.

5. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The factors impacting export success is the main subject area of this study. This specifically addresses Karnataka state's companies especially export-focused manufacturing companies. The survey covers a number of geographic areas, including Jigani, Rjajinagara, Bommasandra, the Peenya industrial area, Electronic City, and other parts of Bengaluru.

6. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To explore the impact of company's export abilities on satisfaction with export success.
2. To evaluate the impact of company's export strategies on satisfaction with export success.

7. HYPOTHESIS

H₀1: There is no significant impact of company's export abilities on satisfaction with export success.

H₁: There is a significant impact of company's export abilities on satisfaction with export success.

H₀2: There is no impact of company's export strategies on satisfaction with export success.

H₂: There is a significant impact of company's export strategies on satisfaction with export success.

8. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

With the aid of the research technique, researchers may think more clearly and make the necessary preparations to collect and assess the pertinent data. It serves as an easy-to-follow framework for conducting research, making the process more cost-effective and efficient (Carrie Williams 2007). Examining the factors that influence export marketing, particularly as they apply to Bengaluru's export-oriented firms, is the aim of this study. All necessary steps in the research process have been finished in order to make the study presentation understandable and important. The selected research approach is based on the descriptive analytical research strategy. To understand the factors influencing export marketing, the study has carefully tackled each objective. Thus, the study's continuous exploration of the influence of marketing strategies on export success leads to the development of an integrated model for the export performance of Bengaluru's export-focused businesses.

i) Primary data

Primary data are those that are newly obtained, for the first time, and that also happen to be unique in nature. The structured questionnaire and interview schedule were the main instruments utilized to gather data for this investigation. The timetable has been developed with consideration for the various elements that impact export success. This specifically addresses Karnataka state's export-focused manufacturers.

ii) Secondary Data

The secondary data was gathered from the following sources, including information from a selection of peer-reviewed articles found in bibliographic databases (Emerald, Sage journals online, Science Direct, Scopus, Taylor & Francis online, Web of Science, and Wiley (online library)). Based on their knowledge validity and greatest influence on the field of study, peer-reviewed journals were taken into consideration. E-Sources Online, publications such as newspapers, periodicals, journals, theses, magazines, and research pieces.

9. SAMPLING UNIT

The study's sample of 100 export managers is taken from a variety of Bengaluru city's export-oriented manufacturing businesses majority of them auto motive component manufacturing companies. Apart from gathering primary data through interview schedules, the researcher also conducts conversations with key accounts managers, supervisors, and technical personnel. The researcher was able to get more useful data about the variables influencing export success thanks to this.

10. SAMPLING METHOD

A stratified sample technique was used in this study to choose individuals for the data collection across the industrial areas in Bengaluru. Every export manager and key accounts manager inside the designated export firms is guaranteed by this way. Questionnaires were randomly sent to export managers in the chosen industrial sector in order to collect data. This method reduces bias,

improves sample representativeness, and allows findings to be generalized. It also guarantees that the gathered data appropriately represents the variety.

11. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Company's Export Abilities and Satisfaction with Export Success

H₀1: There is no significant impact of company's export abilities on satisfaction with export success.

H₁: There is a significant impact of company's export abilities on satisfaction with export success.

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.909 ^a	.826	.802	.52715		
ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	114.574	12	9.548	34.358	.000 ^a
	Residual	24.176	87	.278		
	Total	138.750	99			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.482	.272		23.846	.000
	Company's Digitalization Abilities	-.512	.125	-.438	-4.112	.000
	Management Export Seriousness	-.244	.079	-.261	-3.048	.003
	Firm's Export Knowledge	.119	.136	.087	.868	.389
	Companies infrastructure abilities	.323	.105	.271	3.058	.005
	Company's Export commitment	.262	.090	.231	2.895	.006
	Company's Export Profit	.018	.098	.017	.192	.849
	Company's export entry mode	.009	.082	.007	.093	.927
	Company's Marketing Mix	-.096	.069	-.085	-1.388	.168
	Company's internationalization ability	-.157	.083	-.137	-1.877	.056
	Company's capital investment	-.475	.118	-.392	-4.021	.001
	Type of products for the export business	-.162	.062	-.168	-2.573	.015
	Company's Export goal	-.240	.105	-.183	-2.287	.023

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction with Export success

A multiple regression analysis was used to investigate the impact of 12 variables of Company's Export Abilities on Satisfaction with Export Success. From the above table it is understood that, that Company's Export Abilities (R= .909) indicating high degree of correlation among the variables, t = 23.846, p < .01) had a positively significant effect on Satisfaction with Export success. Hence, it can be concluded that if the average level of Company's Export Abilities were high, the average level of Satisfaction with Export Success would also be high. The analysis also reveals that Company's Export Abilities were able to explain the total variation in Satisfaction with Export Success by the regression model about R² 82.6% being high indicating model fits the data well. Thus answering the hypothesis H₁: There is a significant impact of Company's Export Abilities

on Satisfaction with Export success, posited for this research is accepted. The coefficient table shows the contribution of each Company's Export Abilities. From the above table the beta values demonstrate the unique contribution for the variables such as Company's Digitalization Abilities ($\beta = -.512$) ($p = .000$), Management Export Seriousness ($\beta = -.244$) ($p = .003$), Companies infrastructure abilities ($\beta = .323$) ($p = .005$), Company's Export commitment ($\beta = .262$) ($p = .006$), Company's internationalization ability ($\beta = -.157$) ($p = .056$), Company's capital investment ($\beta = -.475$) ($p = .001$), Type of products for the export business ($\beta = -.162$) ($p = .015$) and Company's Export goal ($\beta = -.240$) ($p = .023$) we're influencing in predicting Satisfaction with Export Success.

Company's Export Strategies and Satisfaction with Export Success.

H₀₂: There is no impact of company's Export strategies on Satisfaction with Export success.

H₂: There is a significant impact of company's Export strategies on Satisfaction with Export success.

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.920 ^a	.847	.822	.49983		
ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	117.515	14	8.394	33.599	.000 ^a
	Residual	21.235	85	.250		
	Total	138.750	99			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.438	.267		24.134	.000
	Export Products without customization	-.382	.125	-.326	-3.054	.004
	Export Products with customization	-.186	.083	-.201	-2.248	.028
	New product development	.057	.130	.043	.454	.652
	Product Drawings based in needs	.446	.107	.374	4.153	.000
	Demand based Pricing	.327	.088	.288	3.713	.000
	Pricing based on Foreign Currency	-.005	.094	-.003	-.039	.968
	Quality based pricing Strategies	-.014	.078	-.015	-.225	.825
	Pricing based on domestic Method	-.058	.066	-.052	-.894	.375
	Distribution by Third party warehousing	-.162	.081	-.142	-1.986	.051
	Export through SBUs	-.573	.118	-.472	-4.862	.000
	Foreign Direct Investment	-.174	.061	-.181	-2.854	.006
	Attend International Exhibitions	-.258	.101	-.198	-2.571	.013
	Conduct Business presentations	-.328	.097	-.347	-3.378	.002
Advertising in business Magazines	.312	.081	.267	3.725	.001	

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction with Export Success

A multiple regression analysis was used to investigate the impact of 14 variables of company's Export strategies on Satisfaction with Export Success. From the above table it is understood that, that company's Export strategies ($R = .920$) indicating high degree of correlation among the

variables, $t = 24.134$, $p < .01$) had a positively significant effect on Satisfaction with Export success. Hence, it can be concluded that if the average level of company's Export strategies were high, the average level of Satisfaction with Export Success would also be high. The analysis also reveals that company's Export strategies were able to explain the total variation in Satisfaction with Export Success by the regression model about R^2 82.6% being high indicating model fits the data well. Thus answering the hypothesis H2: There is a significant impact of company's Export strategies on Satisfaction with Export success, posited for this research is accepted. The coefficient table shows the contribution of each company's Export strategies. From the above table the beta values demonstrate the unique contribution for the variables such as Export Products without customization ($\beta = -.382$) ($P = .004$), Export Products with customization ($\beta = -.186$) ($P = .028$), Product Drawings based in needs ($\beta = .446$) ($P = .000$), Demand based Pricing ($\beta = .327$) ($P = .000$), Distribution by Third party warehousing ($\beta = -.162$) ($P = .051$), Export through SBUs ($\beta = -.573$) ($P = .000$), Foreign Direct Investment ($\beta = -.174$) ($P = .006$), Attend International Exhibitions ($\beta = -.258$) ($P = .013$), Conduct Business presentations ($\beta = -.328$) ($P = .002$) and Advertising in business Magazines ($\beta = .312$) ($P = .001$) we're influencing in predicting Satisfaction with Export Success.

12. RESEARCH FINDINGS

The research revealed that, the unique contribution for the variables such as Company's Digitalization Abilities, Management Export Seriousness, Companies infrastructure abilities, Company's Export commitment, Company's internationalization ability, Company's capital investment, Type of products for the export business and Company's Export goal we're influencing in predicting Satisfaction with Export Success. It is also found that, the unique contribution for the variables such as Export Products without customization, Export Products with customization, Product Drawings based in needs, Demand based Pricing, Distribution by Third party warehousing, Export through SBUs, Foreign Direct Investment, Attend International Exhibitions, Conduct Business presentations and Advertising in business Magazines we're influencing in predicting Satisfaction with Export Success.

INTEGRATED RESEARCH MODEL

13. LIMITATIONS

When answering the questionnaire, some respondents might not generate their own reflection. Only a small percentage of the respondents' key accounts managers and export managers have been reluctant to express their opinions on their export operations. Many responders were hesitant to provide accurate information. In addition to being time-consuming, the research procedure was rather costly. Data gathering was based only on the main data sources. Completing a study of this kind and researching every facet of export marketing was challenging. One of the limitations is the time factor. The study solely looks at factors that impact export orientation in Bangalore City. Only Bengaluru city's manufacturing companies' export operations are the subject of the investigation.

14. SUGGESTIONS

A strong foundation of export expertise is necessary for manufacturing firms to export effectively. This information enhances global competitiveness, lowers risks, and complies with regulations. How a manufacturing company handles foreign markets is greatly influenced by its export motive. The factors that drive a company to export, whether internal or external, frequently influence its export strategy. A manufacturing company's capacity to access and successfully operate in overseas markets is known as its internationalization capabilities, and it is a key component of exporting. These skills, which fall into three categories—strategic, operational, and relational—are frequently developed over time. These talents, which include product adaption, export plan development, and market research and selection, may help a company export effectively. By matching its strengths with the needs of global markets, a manufacturing company may effectively export its goods by utilizing its marketing skills. Good marketing skills assist a company in Determine your target export markets by taking into account economic trends, competition, and demand. Recognize regional differences in consumer preferences. Analyze your competitors to properly position your items. A number of variables, such as the product's nature, delivery schedules, financial limitations, target markets, and legal restrictions, influence the optimal export strategy for producers. the several exporting methods, including direct export, foreign direct investment, strategic business unit formation, third-party logistics, strategic partnerships, order-based manufacturing, etc. Innovation in Products: Differentiate Through Unique Features: When entering highly competitive markets, emphasize new features (such as patented technologies or environmentally friendly materials). Adjust to Local Requirements: Adjust the product to meet the functional or cultural requirements of the intended export market. Leverage Innovation in Marketing: Explain the innovation of your product to international consumers using case studies, narrative, or demonstrations. Apply for International Certifications: In regulated or technical sectors, these increase attractiveness and legitimacy. Foreign currency-based pricing Employ dynamic pricing models: Update export prices often to account for changes in exchange rates. Invoice in Stable Currencies: To reduce risks when selling in nations with volatile currency exchange rates, think about billing in USD or EUR. Use financial tools like forward contracts or currency swaps to protect yourself from currency risk. Examine the

purchasing power of locals: Adjust prices for currency value to reflect what local companies or customers can afford. The cost is determined by the quality of the product. Use tiered pricing to match perceived quality by providing many models or versions at different price ranges. Compare Yourself to Local Rivals: Compare the cost and quality of your product to those of other well-known brands in the target market. Teach Purchasers About Value: Utilize statistics, demos, and brochures to demonstrate how your more expensive, superior product yields a larger return on investment. Provide warranties or guarantees to reassure customers about the longevity of the goods and support high-end pricing. Domestic Rates Utilize as a Baseline: Begin with domestic rates and then account for tariffs, overseas logistics, and compliance expenses. Avoid Direct Price Conversion: Recalculate pricing based on cost structure and market demand rather than immediately translating local prices into foreign currencies. Watch Out for Parallel Imports: If prices fluctuate too much between countries, cheaper items may be reimported, which would affect your local sales. Adapt for Perceived Value: A product that is considered high-end in one market might not be in another; make the necessary adjustments. Technical Magazines (as Research Instruments and Market Channels) Place an Ad in Trade Journals: Use sponsored content and advertisements to connect with decision-makers in niche markets (such as electronics and medical products). Send in case studies or articles: Share technological discoveries or success stories in reputable publications to establish reputation. Utilize for Market Research: Examine publications, advertisements, and product evaluations to determine current trends in your export market or target sector. Find Partners or Distributors: Key players are profiled in a lot of industry periodicals, which is excellent for business development.

15. DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

According to the proposal, a company that wants to expand internationally, is in the early stages of internationalization, or is already in an international market but whose performance falls short of expectations can all benefit from using the integrated export marketing model. Verifying the outcomes in the context of export performance requires multifaceted quantitative analysis. The elements that are not taken into account may be included in the model created for this study, which might lead to valuable research in the future from the standpoint of the export market. Factors affecting the export performance of another industry, both internal and external, can be used to investigate and choose an appropriate marketing plan. It is also possible to view the inclusion of less-tested variables as a positive addition to our understanding of the factors that precede worldwide marketing standardization and adaptation. Because export marketing techniques might differ from instance to case, the study is intended to be expanded by taking into account other case studies in order to generalize the research findings. In order to compare and determine whether there are any other strategies that impact the export performance of small, medium, and large companies during the export marketing strategy formulation process, it is preferable to conduct an investigation by splitting up the auto component manufacturing companies into smaller, medium, and large companies. Trade and investment agreements with present and potential trading partners that might affect manufacturing companies' export

involvement should be carefully examined.

CONCLUSION

According to recent papers, there is a lot of room for more research in the topic of export marketing. There is currently a lack of research on the elements driving export marketing, specifically with regard to Bengaluru's export-oriented industries. By influencing the level of marketing adaptability, this conceptual model indicates the necessity of analyzing the indirect effects of internal and external factors on export marketing strategies and export performance. This approach's justification is that a number of internal and external elements determine how much an export marketing plan should be adjusted. Therefore, it suggests that future export performance research should be analysed as a function of the fit between the firm's environment and the selected export marketing strategy. Comparing how marketing strategy affects export performance and vice versa may be a topic for future study. One of the main issues with the research is how export performance is conceptualized and measured. This disagreement on how to define and quantify export success makes it extremely challenging, if not impossible, to compare the results of various research. Therefore, it is proposed that testing this model, or a specific connection based on it, across many sectors, nations, and regions, as well as with various units and statistical analysis techniques, would be a profitable avenue for future study. This theoretical framework may also help managers enhance their company's export success.

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